

Implementation of Government Goods and Services Procurement using the E-Purchasing Method in the Tegal Religious Court: Mediating Role of Supply Chain in Indonesia

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Abstract-Program Postgraduate Program in Pancasakti University Tegal. 2019. Implementation of Procurement of Government Goods and Services by E- Purchasing Method in the Tegal Religious Court. The implementation of e-procurement in various agencies makes the process of interaction between users and service providers, and the community-run easier and accelerates the process of procurement of goods. Equally important, the implementation of e-procurement has automatically improved the control system for various rules and violations. Procurement of government goods/services electronically can be done by e- tendering and e-purchasing who use electronic catalogs and supply chain plays a vital role in the e-purchasing of the goods and services. The purpose of this study is 1) examine the implementation of e-purchasing in the application of rules regarding the procurement process of goods/services through the Tegal Religious Court, 2) explain the role of supervisory institutions in the implementation of the procurement process of goods in the Tegal Religious Court in anticipation of fraud that can cause losses to the state's finances. This type of research is normative-empirical legal research using a normative approach. The type of material used is primary, secondary and tertiary legal materials. Data collection methods used are library research and field studies. The results of this study include 1) procurement of goods/services with e-purchasing method is the right system in implementing procurement because it is more transparent, effective, efficient, compared to conventional systems, but the implementation is not optimal because a) is still coordinated so that time is not enough efficient, b) in e-catalog there is no information on the number of items available, so the buyer does not know the stock directly, c) the Supreme Court has

not precisely targeted domestic production due to high specifications, 2) the role of supervisory institutions is not optimal because there are still many frauds and not yet the maximum application of a whistleblower because the procurement executors and the wider community are not familiar with the procurement of goods/services.

Keywords; Procurement of goods and services, E-purchasing, the electronic catalog

1. Introduction

The procurement of goods and services is essentially a party that supports the user to obtain the desired goods or services using certain methods and processes to obtain an agreement on price, time, and other agreements. While supply chain management gives support to the purchasing related matters of the organization that also supports the e-purchasing process. So that the goods and services provided can be made properly, thus Side parties, namely the users and providers must always be guided by the philosophy of procurement of goods and services, ethical requirements and rules with the principles of procurement, methods, and processes of procurement of goods and services that are standard[1]. Procurement that uses suppliers of goods and services both as business entities and individuals, when done through the selection of providers of goods and services. The supply chain considers as an effective tool in the procurement of goods and services. Government procurement of goods and services is carried out directly by procurement officials by purchasing[2].

Goods or pay for services directly to providers of goods and services, without going through an auction or selection process. Direct procurement is the usual buying and selling between providers that have goods and services for sale and procurement representatives who need related goods and services to carry out transactions of goods and services at special prices.

A good system of goods and services procurement is a system of goods and services procurement that applies the principles of good governance, effective and efficient governance, and structuring the safety of the three pillars (government, private, and community) in the implementation of governance and supply chain practices. Efficient procurement of goods and services needs to be endeavored by using funds and minimal power to achieve quality and targets within the specified time or using funds that have been determined to achieve results and targets with maximum quality, can be used to procure goods and services that are in accordance with the Needs and targets determined by providing comparable benefits[3].

To create quality public services at a low cost, the Indonesian government has issued national development policies and strategies through Presidential Instruction No. 3/2003, which contains a legal umbrella of all technical policies in the e-government sector. Therefore, in supporting the implementation of good governance, now in every government institution is required to use the application of e-procurement services.

2. Literature Review

In the competition of globalization about the growth of any organization or a company, various procedures are adopted for the differential piece of work, where the ways of such purpose also form different aspects through which it can be accomplished. Besides this, a complete channel is also established while reviewing past work in the same era not for the efficiencies but also the easy ways. Procurement is the main channel that not only opens the area of acquiring goods from different sources but it has also become the area of acquiring services through established channels that support efficient ways for the organizations. The organizations themselves also utilize the same methods for adaptation, though governments of the countries are also well acquainted with the same perspectives, where the supply chain has also enabled the achievement of aims regarding the scenarios of goods and services, while the objectives could hide to achieve in no time.

Based on the above, an electronic procurement was born which was then abbreviated as e-procurement as a process of procurement of goods and services by the government which was carried out electronically and internet-based using communication and information facilities.6 through the e-procurement system[3], the process of procurement of government goods/services can

be carried out effectively, efficiently, openly, competitively, transparently, fairly, and accountably so that it is expected to be able to free and reduce the obligation to purchase goods and services that involve state finances[4].

Some things that need to be considered so that Government Goods / Services Procurement can be transparent are:

1. All regulations/policies / administrative rules/procedures and practices undertaken (including the selection of procurement methods) must be transparent to all prospective participants;

2. Opportunities

3. The winner must be transparent to all potential participants.

Some things that must be considered so that the Procurement of Goods / Services is accountable are:

1. The existence of complete records and records;

2. The existence of a monitoring system to enforce the rules;

3. There is a mechanism for evaluating, reviewing, researching and taking action on protests and complaints made by participants [5]. Where through the program, all central and regional government agencies are required to implement e-procurement in the implementation of procurement of goods and services[6]. Therefore, e-procurement is one of the most effective ways to improve management, both directly and indirectly, in finding sources of purchase, so that e-procurement will increase the key to success in increasing future competitiveness.

The goods and services are the main are in different organizations, either government also evolves such attainments where the services and goods are procured through variant ways while such procurement also requires the process of supply chain management for the use of such goods and services. Most of the goods and services are provided through paper posts, while the acquiring was also however linked with the same, therefore in the current era, many studies have introduced the process of E system which helped the procedure of procurement. Various posts are introduced through E purchasing and electronic catalogs, while their appointments are entailed with the same policies and procedures. In the Tegal religious courts, women are procured to sustain the environment of religious matters whereby the system of E purchasing and electronic catalog helped the feasibility[7]. The implementation through the Tegal courts has not only enabled the proper rulings but also has achieved the effectiveness of such implementing measures.

In general, the implementation of the procurement of goods and services can be grouped based on the resilience of its activities. The stages of the procurement of goods and services are grouped into 4 (four) stages, namely:

1. Preparation Phase, at this stage the activities include:

- a. Planning the procurement of goods and services,
- b. Establishment of a committee or appointment of officials for the procurement of goods and services,
- c. Stage of contract preparation,
- d. Stage of contract implementation.

2. Procurement Process Phase, at this stage the activities include:

- a. The selection of providers of goods and services,
 - b. Determination of goods and service providers.
3. Contract Preparation Phase;
4. Contract Implementation Stage.

In its journey, the procurement of goods/services electronically using the e-purchasing method, namely the purchase of goods/services through an electronic catalog, has not yet found obstacles. In this study, the authors are interested in finding out more about the implementation of government procurement of goods/services through the electronic system (e-procurement) with the e-purchasing method compared to procurement of goods/services using conventional methods and the extent of the role of supervisory institutions in the procurement process and government services in anticipation of fraud that can cause state financial losses, the authors consider the need for a study under the title "Implementation of Government Goods and Services Procurement with the E-Purchasing Method in the Tegal Religious Court".

The conceptual framework in this study illustrates the concepts taken as a basis in research conducted on the procurement of government goods/services using e-purchasing methods.

Figure 1. Goods / Services Procurement Needs

Based on the picture above Government Goods / Services Procurement can be done in two ways, namely Self-Management and Providers. Self-management is the procurement of goods/services whose work is planned, worked and supervised by the K / L / D / I as the person in charge of the budget, other government agencies and/or community groups. The e-purchasing method is part of the provider selection method by the non-auction method in addition to the direct appointment method and direct procurement.

Figure 2. Procurement of Goods / Services electronically (e-procurement)

To find out the extent of the implementation of government goods/services procurement by the e-purchasing method, it is necessary to know the rules that govern and how they are applied in the implementation of government goods/services procurement. To clarify and deepen the discussion of this writing the Legal Effectiveness Theory is used. The term legal effectiveness theory comes from an English translation, namely the effectiveness of the legal theory, the Dutch language is called affectivities van de juridischetheories, the German language, namely *wirksamkeit der rechtlichentheories*[8]. [9]presents a definition of legal effectiveness: Do people act according to a way to avoid sanctions that are threatened by legal norms or not, and whether sanctions are implemented if the conditions are met or not met. Antony Allot stated about the effectiveness of law: Law will be effective if the purpose of its existence and application can prevent undesirable actions that can eliminate chaos[10]. Effective law, in general, can make what is designed can be realized. If there is a failure, then the possibility of easy rectification occurs if there is a need to implement or apply the law in a different new atmosphere, the law will be able to resolve it.

From these opinions on the Legal Effectiveness Theory, we will get a related relationship between the rules governing the procurement of government goods/services with the e-purchasing method and the implementation process, can it run well or have many obstacles or deficiencies.

The data collection method is very close to the data source because through this data collection the data needed will be obtained for further analysis as expected. The data collection method in this research is literature study and field study.

a. Literature Study

Literature study aims to study, research, and trace secondary data including primary material, namely legal material that provides an explanation of primary legal material and tertiary legal material, namely material that provides guidance or explanation on primary and secondary legal material

b. Field Study

Field studies are data collection directly at the research location by taking research material from applicable regulations, procurement documents, interviews, applications and websites related to the electronic procurement process (e-purchasing), as well as literature relating to government procurement of goods/services with the e-purchasing method in the Tegal Religious Court.

Analysis of the data in this study in the form of an assessment of the results of data processing to obtain conclusions from the results of a study. The data obtained will be collected and analyzed into a synergistic and integrated discussion data so that it is easy to understand. In this study, researchers used a qualitative analysis method viewed from an empirical point of view which was used to analyze data obtained through library studies [11]. The empirical analysis produces a description of the position and role of law in the implementation of procurement of goods / services electronically in government agencies [12]. The purpose of the analysis is to provide input as well as a solution to the obstacles that exist in an effort to broaden the normative legal perspective that is related to regulating the procurement of goods/services through electronic systems at government agencies as well as the role of supervisory institutions in the implementation of the procurement process of goods and services in anticipating the occurrence of fraud that can cause state financial losses [13].

H1: These is positive association among the procurement of goods and services and tegal religious courts.

H2: These is positive association among the E-purchasing and tegal religious courts.

H3: These is positive association among the electronic catalog and tegal religious courts.

H4: Supply Chain Management has positive mediation among the links of procurement of goods and services and tegal religious courts.

H5: Supply Chain Management has positive mediation among the links of E-purchasing and tegal religious courts.

H6: Supply Chain Management has positive mediation among the links of electronic catalog and tegal religious courts.

3. Research Methods

The questionnaires method was adopted by the existing study to collect the data while PLS-SEM was adopted for the evolution of the data. The procurement of goods and services (PGS) has 20 items, E-purchasing (EP) has 15 items, electronic catalog (EC) has 10 items, supply chain management (SCM) has 6 items and tegal religious court (TRC) has 10 items. These constructs are highlighted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Theoretical Framework

4. Result

The items of this study are extensively linked with each other because the loadings and AVE are higher than 0.50 while Alpha and CR are not lower than 0.70 and these figures are highlighted in Table 1 given below:

Table 1: Convergent Validity

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
Tegal Religious Court	TRC1	0.566	0.923	0.935	0.586
	TRC10	0.783			
	TRC2	0.765			
	TRC3	0.844			
	TRC4	0.634			
	TRC5	0.807			
	TRC6	0.804			
	TRC7	0.786			
	TRC8	0.813			
	TRC9	0.805			
Procurement of goods and services	PGS1	0.844	0.963	0.974	0.645
	PGS10	0.794			
	PGS11	0.767			
	PGS12	0.823			
	PGS13	0.794			
	PGS14	0.834			
	PGS15	0.816			
	PGS16	0.806			
	PGS17	0.717			
	PGS18	0.783			
	PGS2	0.822			
	PGS20	0.765			
	PGS3	0.794			
	PGS4	0.843			
	PGS5	0.842			
	PGS6	0.824			
	PGS7	0.836			
	PGS8	0.808			
	PGS9	0.704			
	E-Purchasing	EP1			
EP10		0.705			
EP11		0.749			
EP13		0.688			
EP15		0.811			
EP2		0.783			
EP3		0.796			
EP4		0.743			
EP5		0.795			
EP6		0.713			
EP7	0.522				
EP8	0.735				
EP9	0.805				
Supply Chain Management	SCM1	0.954	0.959	0.968	0.834
	SCM2	0.826			
	SCM3	0.954			

	SCM4	0.955			
	SCM5	0.828			
	SCM6	0.956			
Electronic Catalog	EC1	0.824	0.936	0.943	0.667
	EC10	0.575			
	EC2	0.855			
	EC3	0.846			
	EC4	0.817			
	EC5	0.864			
	EC6	0.865			
	EC7	0.854			
	EC8	0.776			

The constructs of this study are not extensively linked with each other because the Heterotrait Monotrait ratios are smaller than 0.90 and these figures are highlighted in Table 2 given below:

Table 2: Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio

	TRC	PGS	EP	SCM	EC
TRC					
PGS	0.539				
EP	0.153	0.080			
SCM	0.527	0.902	0.061		
EC	0.450	0.479	0.110	0.425	

Figure 4: Measurement Model Assessment

The results of the path analysis show that PGS and EC have a positive association with the TRC and accept H1 and H3. In addition, SCM has positive mediation among the nexus of PGS and TRC, EP and TRC, and EC and TRC and accept H4, H5, and H6. These statistics are highlighted in Table 3.

Table 3: Path Analysis

	Beta	S.D.	t-values	p-values	L.L.	U.L.
PGS -> TRC	0.208	0.105	1.991	0.025	0.031	0.364
EP -> TRC	-	0.065	2.189	0.015	0.228	-0.025
EC -> TRC	0.214	0.074	3.107	0.001	0.115	0.342
PGS -> SCM -> TRC	0.204	0.086	2.482	0.004	0.067	0.333
EP -> SCM -> TRC	0.038	0.004	3.884	0.001	0.002	0.035
EC -> SCM -> TRC	0.041	0.003	5.371	0.000	0.015	0.016

Figure 5: Structural Model Assessment

5. Discussion

In research on the Implementation of Government Goods and Services Procurement using the E-Purchasing method in the Tegal Religious Court, the authors take data on the procurement of goods / services in the 2018 fiscal year that procures data processing and communication equipment in the form of a laptop with the e-purchasing method through an electronic catalog (e - catalog) which goes through several stages, namely:

1. Making a General Procurement Plan

Before the procurement of goods / services is carried out, a planner must first be made. What is needed, what is the budget provided and the specifications of the goods / services to be held? In the case of the implementation of procurement of goods / services must be published the first List of Budget Implementation Filling (DIPA) of the current year, then we are required to make and announce the General Procurement Plan so that the budget that we will carry out in the year that will run can be realized (Sriyakul, Umam, & Jermstittiparsert, 2019b). If it is not made and announced then the budget will be blocked because it cannot be monitored. Making and announcing a Procurement General Plan is required for the Budget User Authority to aim for providers of goods/services to have time to prepare themselves as well as evidence that the Ministry / Institution / Regional Government has carried out the basic principles of procurement of goods/services that are open and transparent.

In terms of procurement of goods/services we make a Procurement General Plan, we use the Procurement General Information System Application (SIRUP), which each work unit has access rights. There are 2 access rights that are logged in as a Commitment Making Officer (PPK) make a General Procurement Plan (RUP) and logging in as a Budget User Authority (KPA) to validate a Commitment Making Officer (PPK) who can carry out the making of a General Procurement Plan (RUP) and announced the General Procurement Plan (RUP) that has been made.

For the procurement of procurement using the e-purchasing method, it is required that when making a package in the Procurement General Plan an e-purchasing method must be chosen, this is done so that the procurement package can be read by the system when making the procurement package on the Electronic Catalog Application (e-catalog). After the package is completed (Networks, Channels, Participation, Moreno, & Trejo, 2019), the Commitment Making Officer (PPK) is then announced by the Budget User Authority (KPA).

Based on an interview with H. Mohamad Subchan, SH, Secretary of the Tegal Religious Court as the Budget User Authority, stated that if the General Procurement Plan had not been made by the work unit, it would be included in monitoring from the center because the budget could not be realized, especially if there were procurement using e-purchasing cannot be carried out because the work unit does not have a Package ID for making the e-purchasing procurement package.

2. Appointment of Goods / Services Procurement Officer (PPBJ)

In the appointment of Goods / Services Procurement Officer (PPBJ), the Tegal Religious Court applies to the Procurement Service Unit (ULP) coordinator of the Central Java region to assign one of the ULP members as a Procurement Service Unit (ULP) to the Tegal Religious Court. In 2018 acting as the ULP coordinator for the Central Java region was the Central Java High Court. After the ULP receives the request, then appoints a ULP member who will be assigned to be a Goods / Services Procurement Officer at the Tegal Religious Court.

After obtaining a letter of appointment for the Goods / Services Procurement Officer from ULP to carry out the procurement of goods/services, then the Budget User Authority (KPA) of the Tegal Religious Court makes a decision letter regarding the appointment of the Goods / Services Procurement Officer assigned to the Tegal Religious Court (America, Role, Chac, Giancarlo, & Orozco, 2019). After the issuance of the decree made, the appointed procurement official can begin to carry out the procurement of goods/services in the Tegal Religious Court.

3. Selection of providers

In selecting a provider, first look for goods/services in accordance with technical specifications that have been determined by Echelon I in the electronic catalog (e-catalog). In the selection of goods that are in accordance with the specifications and selection of providers based on the Estimated Self Price (HPS) determined by the Commitment Making Officer (PPK). Choosing suppliers and goods to be purchased is done through an electronic catalog (e-catalog) which is located at <https://lpse.mahkamahagung.go.id/> by logging in the Commitment Making Official (PPK).

After entering the item implementation menu using the e-purchasing method, then just choose and determine the goods and their supplies in an electronic catalog (e-catalog) following the specifications and Estimated Self Price (HPS) that have been determined. In selecting suppliers and selecting goods to be purchased, it requires carefulness, because the items chosen are very many and from various kinds of providers. Between 2015 and 2018, the selection of e-purchasing providers was held jointly at the Semarang High Court of Religion.

4. Making a procurement package

After determining the goods to be purchased and their supply, the Commitment Making Officer (PPK) asks the Goods / Services Procurement Officer (PPBJ) who has been appointed by the Procurement Services Unit (ULP) who then makes the package. In making packages need to be considered as:

- a. Desired goods specifications,
- b. Available budget ceiling,
- c. Self-Estimated Price (HPS) determined by the Commitment Making Officer (PPK),
- d. Package ID in the General Procurement Plan (RUP) that has been made,
- e. Other data about work units and goods/services procurement officials,
- f. The Goods / Services Procurement Officer can negotiate the price of the goods to be purchased.

Based on an interview with Akbar Syaiful, S.H., as the Procurement Officer, he explained when making the package must be available and knew in advance the package ID that was made on the Procurement General Plan that had been announced. Implementation of making a package of value under Rp. 200,000,000. - (Two hundred million rupiahs) is carried out by the Procurement Officer, whereas if the procurement value is above Rp. 200,000,000. - (Two hundred million rupiahs) carried out by the Commitment Making Officer (PPK) .79

5. KDP agreements with providers

After the package of goods/services procurement using the e-purchasing method is made, the Goods / Services Procurement Officer reports that he has made the procurement package and returns it to the Committing Officer (PPK) to "agree" to make the package. After approval, it is the provider's turn to approve the making of the package whether it is continued or not (Rufaidah, AtIrsyadi, Saregar, & Umam, 2018). If it has been agreed, then an agreement is reached between the two parties in the procurement of goods/services by the e-purchasing method and after that, it is stated in the order letter and agreement letter (contract) containing the agreement and the agreement of both parties regarding the purchase of an item with specifications, price, and a specified implementation period.

6. Implementation of the Agreement

After the procurement of goods/services using the e-purchasing method is carried out online, the Goods / Services Procurement Officer (PPBJ) prepares documents such as Order Letters and Agreement Letters (Contracts) as to completeness in the process of procurement of goods/services. Electronically enough to just order online then just wait for the items ordered earlier to arrive, but in the responsibility of disbursing the budget, physical documents are still needed. This is a form of prudence and as a form of black and white, there has been an agreement on the sale and purchase of goods between the Goods / Services Procurement Officer (PPBJ) with the Provider. The length of the fulfillment of needs/delivery of goods that have been purchased depends on the agreement that has been done.

7. Check and Handover of Goods / Services Procurement Goods

If the goods purchased have arrived at their destination, then what needs to be done is to check the goods that arrive are in accordance with what is ordered, especially the specifications, then check the condition and completeness of the goods. The inspection and receipt of the goods shall be carried out by the Receiver / Examiner of the Work Result that has been appointed by the Tegal Religious Court Budget User Authority, then the results will be stated in an official inspection and receipt of goods.

As said by NurKhikmah, S.H.I. as the Examining Officer and Recipient of Work Results (PPHP) during the interview that when the goods purchased have been received, then we open the packaging first to check the condition and completeness of the goods, for example we buy a laptop then we check the item first, the laptop can turn on or not, can be operated, the specifications are also in accordance with the order, as well as accessories such as chargers, driver CDs, manuals, and storage bags

If the goods have been received and have been inspected by the Recipient / Examining Official of the Tegal Religious Court, the Provider will send a letter requesting payment to the Tegal Religious Court to immediately make the payment. The sending of the request for payment is usually accompanied by a tax invoice and a Tax Payment Form (SSP) used as an attachment when submitting payments to the State Treasury and Service Office (KPPN).

1. The Party that Oversees the Implementation of the procurement of Goods / Services

a. Supreme Court Supervisory Agency (BAWAS) RI

The Oversight Body has the task of carrying out the highest supervision of the actions of the court within the judiciary environment under it according to the Law and overseeing the behavior and actions of the judges and the judiciary in carrying out the duties of the court.

The functions of the Supervisory Agency include:

1) To keep the implementation of the duties of the judiciary in accordance with the plans and provisions of the applicable legislation,

2) Control that financial administration, justice are managed in an orderly manner and the judicial apparatus performs their duties properly and correctly,

3) Ensuring the implementation of excellent and transparent and accountable public services,

4) Minimizing the occurrence of errors and gaps between work standards and the performance of duties in the judiciary,

5) Measuring the level of compliance and obedience of judicial authorities in carrying out planning with the available budget in order to assess the achievement of performance in order to make it easier for leaders to take corrective actions and subsequent planning.

The Oversight Body's authority includes,

1) Conduct routine / regular supervision, finance and handling public complaints,

2) conduct a financial review of the competitiveness of the work in the Supreme Court and the lower judicial body,

3) Perform other supervisory duties assigned by the leadership of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia.

One of the objectives of the Supervisory Agency is to implement a monitoring mechanism for the administration of justice that is free from Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism (KKN) practices and the handling of public complaints in a transparent, accountable, effective, and efficient manner. This includes the implementation of the procurement of goods / services which is the implementation of the budget realization (Rodríguez-ponce & Rodríguez-ponce, 2019). In carrying out its supervision, every year guidance and supervision is carried out directly to the judicial work unit under the Indonesian Supreme Court, while monthly routine supervision throughout the year is carried out by monitoring the performance of each work unit through manual and application reports. In addition, the Supervisory Agency also receives complaints from every apparatus of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia and from the wider community through the SIWAS Application at <https://siwas.mahkamahagung.go.id/>.

c. Supreme Audit Agency (BPK)

Article 23 E Paragraph 1 of the 1945 Constitution mandates the function of auditing the management and responsibility of state finances by the State Audit Board (BPK) which is an institution that directly oversees and examines state financial policies including the use of the state budget for procurement of goods / services carried out by the government. It's very strategic and honorable function places the Supreme Audit Board (BPK) as an institution that consistently maintains its objectivity. In supporting the task of the Supreme Audit Board (BPK),

Law Number 15 of 2004 concerning the Audit of Management and Responsibility of State Finances was issued.

As stipulated in the 1945 Constitution, the audit which is the task of the Supreme Audit Board (BPK) includes an examination of the management and responsibilities regarding state finances which include:

1) Financial Examination is an examination of government financial statements carried out in order to provide an expression of opinion about the reasonableness of the information presented in the government financial statements.

2) Performance inspection is an examination of economic and efficiency aspects as well as an examination of the effectiveness aspects that are commonly carried out for the benefit of management by the government internal supervisory apparatus.

3) Examination with a specific purpose is an examination carried out with special objectives, outside of financial audits and performance audits. Included in the examination of this particular purpose is an examination of other matters relating to finance and investigative investigations.

Provisions regarding the examination of state expenditure management are contained in Article 2 of Law No. 15 of 2004 which states that:

1) An examination of state finances includes an examination of the management of state finances and an examination of the state's financial responsibilities.

2) The Supreme Audit Board (BPK) carries out audits of the management and responsibilities of state finances.

Based on this article, the scope of the examination that is the task of the Financial Audit Agency (BPK) covers the examination of management and responsibilities regarding state finances. The scope of the examination becomes very broad because it is authorized to carry out the budget (pre audit) and budget accountability (post audit). The audit covers all elements of state finance as referred to in Article 2 of Law Number 17 of 2003 concerning State Finance. In carrying out audits of the management and responsibility of state finances, the State Audit Board (BPK) can utilize the results of examinations by the government internal control apparatus. For the purposes of inspection, the report on the results of government internal audits must be submitted to the Supreme Audit Board (BPK). In carrying out the inspection task, an auditor or expert from outside the Supreme Audit Board (BPK) who works for and on behalf of the Supreme Audit Board (BPK) is used. In the framework of financial / performance audits, inspectors conduct tests and assessments of the implementation of the government's internal control system[14,19]. Investigators can carry out investigative examinations to reveal indications of state losses or the existence of criminal elements. Reports on the results of audits of

government financial statements contain opinions. The report on the results of the inspection of the performance contains findings, conclusions and recommendations. Reports on the results of examinations with specific objectives contain conclusions.

Responses from government officials responsible for the examiner's findings, conclusions and recommendations are published or attached to the audit report. The official is obliged to follow up on the recommendations of the inspection report. Officials are required to provide answers or explanations to the Supreme Audit Board (BPK) regarding follow-up on recommendations in the audit report. The answer to the results of the inspection is submitted to the Supreme Audit Board (BPK) no later than 60 (sixty) days after the audit report is received. The Supreme Audit Board (BPK) monitors the implementation of follow-up results of audits and officials found not to carry out obligations may be subject to administrative sanctions in accordance with statutory provisions.

The Supreme Audit Board (BPK) issued a decree setting the time limit of the treasurer's responsibility for the shortage of cash / goods that occurred, after knowing there were deficiencies in the procurement of goods / services that were detrimental to the country's finances[15-16]. The treasurer can submit objections / self-defense to the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK) within 14 (fourteen) working days after receiving the state loss decree. If the treasurer does not submit objections / self-defense is rejected, the Supreme Audit Board (BPK) determines the decision letter on the compensation of the state to the treasurer concerned.

The audit of the procurement of goods / services can be done when the implementation process and when the procurement of goods / services has been completed. Auditing goods / services procurement in principle aims to ensure whether the party being audited has followed the policies / regulations in force.

Based on the results of the study in the previous chapter, the authors conclude that the procurement of goods / services electronically (e-procurement) with the e-purchasing method is the right system used in the procurement of goods / services because it is more transparent, effective, and efficient when compared to the procurement of goods / conventional system services (face to face). The current legal regulations regarding e-purchasing are felt to be ineffective because they are still not specific, both in terms of substance and technicality because the implementation and emphasis are not yet optimal, so there is a need to update the rules that govern and emphasize the obligation to use them.

Procurement has gained much importance rather than purchasing of goods and services, the proper channel has enabled the establishment of systems the work on the basis of tasks assigned. Authors have mentioned some

transparent ways which has improved the quality of such procurement, while the effectiveness and efficiency has also gained value through variant researchers. As compared to the conventional systems of running government, such procurement project has more feasibility with prevailing effectiveness. Such effectiveness has not only prevented many means of making frauds but also has restrained many wrongdoings.

While analyzing the views on goods and services procured through viable means, many significant results have been appraised linking supply chain management as an effective mean of supporting the Tegal Religious Courts and other E systems of procurement. Various channels have been found improper as compared to E purchasing and electronic catalog, whereas the efficiencies have also been measured through the study which enables the supply chain between such factors as a positive element striving for the implementations. Despite of breaking the rules while making violations, certain electronic systems with the help of supply chain has endorsed significant measures for effective and efficient procurement [17-19].

The implementation of e-purchasing at the Tegal Religious Court was good enough from the beginning to the end of its procurement. Starting from making the General Procurement Plan (RUP) prior to the implementation of the current year, the appointment of the Goods / Services Procurement Officer, the selection of providers, making the procurement package, until the payment process is in accordance with applicable regulations. Regarding the weaknesses of the implementation of procurement of goods / services by e-purchasing method in the Tegal Religious Court, namely the time that is felt to be not yet sufficiently efficient due to, among others: (a) The implementation is coordinated by the regional coordinator of the Semarang High Court so that the purchases are carried out collectively and in large quantities automatically also have to wait for all the needs as many as the desired amount is met, then only the goods are sent by the provider to be distributed, (b) the Supreme Court in issuing the specifications of the goods needed is considered high enough, so it is not right to lead to the use of the produce domestic production and also the specifications of the goods needed are only a few vendors or brands that provide them, so that they are items that are difficult to find in the market and finally take a long time to distribute.

In the implementation of supervision in the Tegal Religious Court it can be concluded that: (a) The Supreme Court Supervisory Board (BAWAS) The Republic of Indonesia Supreme Court always oversees the budget realization of each judicial work unit under the Supreme Court of Indonesia by monitoring the application of monitoring and evaluation of budget realization, and directly to the work unit. However, the role of the

Supervisory Agency (BAWAS) and other oversight institutions is not yet optimal because there are still some administrative errors found in the documents and technicalities when filing the disbursement of funds that hinders the realization of the budget. (b) The use of the whistleblower application is still not optimal because the executors of the procurement of goods / services of the government and the wider community lack understanding and are still confused about the procurement of goods / services especially about the use of the whistleblowing system application which is still not accustomed to its use. Broadly speaking, the inspection and supervision is only based on reports and existing documents.

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